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THE IMPORTANCE OF ASSESSMENT IN EFL TEACHING

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Annotation: The importance of assessment in teaching English is a essential topic nowadays. In this article, I would like to show the importance of assessment process in effective language learning. Assessment is an inevitable condition for effective learning. There are many ways to evaluate student’s knowledge but I singled out the most effective tests, this method of measuring a person’s abilities, knowledge or results in a certain area.

Keywords: assessment, effective, evaluate, test, knowledge

ВАЖНОСТИ ОЦЕНИВАНИЯ В ОБУЧЕНИЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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Аннотация: важность оценки в изучении английского языка является одной из ключевых тем в наше время. В этой статье я хотела бы показать важность процесса оценивания эффективности изучения языка. Оценка является неизбежным условием эффективного обучения. Существует множество способов оценки знаний студента ,наиболее эффективным являются тесты. Это метод измерения способностей, знаний или результатов человека в определенной области.

Ключевые слова: оценка, эффективность, давать оценку, проверка, знания

Introduction

“Is this going to be on the test?” “How will we be assessed?” Students and learners always ask these kinds of questions. The reason of that because they want to know how their teacher is going to evaluate them. The question arises about the importance of assessment and evaluation. Educators use assessment to provide instruction and feedback that will help students improve. A coherent and transparent assessment and evaluation are necessary to focus both teachers and students on predetermined goals and outcomes. In English language teaching, it is very important to design performance assessments that capture samples

It is the professional and personal responsibility of teachers to analyze, evaluate, reflect on, and improve their classroom practice (Desimone & Garet, 2016). Tests have a way of scaring students. The anticipation of the upcoming “moment of truth” results in anxiety and self-doubt along with a fervent hope. The fear of failure is perhaps one of the strongest negative emotions a student can experience, and the most common instrument inflicting such fear is the test. Students are not likely to view a test as positive, pleasant or affirming.

Assessments seem as unavoidable in all educational settings around the world. Courses of study in every discipline are marked by the periodic milestones of progress that have become conventional methods of measurement. Assessment is a popular and sometimes misunderstood term in current educational practice. In educational practice, assessment is an ongoing process that encompasses a wide range of methodological techniques. Historically, the practice of evaluating teaching performance based on Self-Assessment (SA) has been considered of little value and viewed as offering more problems than solutions for reflective practitioners (Barber, 1990). According to Reagan and Osborn (2002, p. 22), “reflective practice can best be understood as a cyclical process, moving from reflection-for-practice through reflection-in-practice and on to reflection-on-practice, which then leads on to new reflection-for-practice”. In this paper, I would like to discuss the importance of assessment and evaluation process in effective language teaching [1-6].

Assessment Strategies and Their Purposes

Assessment is an unavoidable must for learning effectively. There are five key facets of learning: curiosity, sociality, emotion, authenticity, failure. (Eyler, 2018) Two of these facets are strongly connected with assessment and evaluation. In Chapter 4, focused on authenticity, Eyler defines authentic learning contexts as close to the “real world” as possible and students have to use “real-world” tools, techniques, and interactions to address challenges or solve problems. He argues that such contexts offer better opportunities for learning than artificial ones. Assessments must be as authentic and immersive as possible for optimal learning results. Assignments that are as authentic as possible give students the opportunity to learn through experience. Eyler concludes: “The brain doesn’t mess around. If it registers a situation as being artificial or unimportant, it will allocate cognitive resources elsewhere” (Eyler, 2018, p. 170) [7].

Teachers must attentively develop series of assessment that provides students with everything, such as feedback, goals for the improvement and evaluation. Thus, assessment can be considered as a pedagogical challenge for educators. It is accepted that behind any pedagogical decision is an image of prototypical students, also known as imagined audience, which embodies a set of assumptions regarding the profile of students, such as their background, their (lack of) knowledge, their needs and their ultimate aim upon graduation. (Selvi, 2012)

A well-organized assessment must contain levels of formative and summative assessments. Formative assessment may provide quick learning checks to find out whether students have learned and can use specific language elements, such as new vocabulary and grammar. Susan Brookhart contrasted formative and summative assessment in this way: “Formative assessment means information gathered and reported for use in the development of knowledge and skills, and summative assessment means information gathered and reported for use in judging the outcome of that development” (Brookhart, 2004, p.45). Summative assessment inspires greater confidence, the skills acquired and the knowledge gained. Summative assessment present students with a new application of the skills. It is important to keep in mind that no single assessment instrument is enough to provide students and teachers with all the information needed to identify what to do next.

Assessment-based Feedback and Motivation

Instructors not only guide regarding assessment content, but also students’ post-assessment efforts. Students will know what they need to learn from each activity and the language elements that are needed to be

successful. Every assessment must be followed by evaluation and feedback. Motivation also comes from the evaluation. When students receive feedback on a performance, they know which qualities they demonstrated strongly or weakly. Assessment-based feedback assists students in identifying what they need to do to improve.

According to Brunson (2017), effective assessment arises from a teacher's desire to become a better practitioner in the classroom and entails a "systematic and comprehensive approach to instructional improvement" (p. 5) that teachers can employ in a "self-directed" manner (p. 5). This outlook, which combines willingness, openness, and initiative, also serves as the foundation for the development and practice of our approach to assessment and post-assessment practices. Only instructors who are willing to enhance their teaching through continual self-reflection on their areas for improvement will be successful in this endeavor. We can implement this perspective in our practice to modify teachers' perspective on teaching and their approach to classroom practice in Turkmenistan. This approach suggests teachers not only to be spectators, but active participants in professional development and they are expected to make recommendations for further improvement.

Feedback to the assessment is not always positive. Thus, learners should be ready for the negative feedback as well. Failure in assessment should not be seen as discouraging put-back in learning. The final chapter of the book by Eyler (2018) focuses on failure, a topic not often treated positively in educational settings. When he was a student himself, Eyler was "certainly never rewarded for [his] failures" (p. 173), and even in graduate school, he remained unaware of the important possibilities that failure offers for learning. In early childhood, failure leads to novel techniques and newdiscoveries. While failure's inherent potential for learning – as "a source of joyful experimentation" (p. 180) – does not change, students' attitudes toward failure do begin to change as they start school and begin experiencing failure as something for which they will be corrected, shamed, or punished. Eyler offers many examples of how failure, rather than success, can lead to better learning outcomes. At the end of the chapter, Eyler turns the conversation to "the elephant in the room" (p.212), in other words grades. "Grades", he writes, "seem like a good idea, and on the surface they appear to have the potential to be useful, but by the end they subvert all the work you have been trying to do" (p. 212). Grades "stigmatize failure" (p. 213), and thus function only as an "extrinsic motivator, whereas educational pursuits need to be primarily

intrinsic if they are to be transformational” (p. 213). Eyer encourages readers to change their grading models. This approach to assessment offers students the freedom to take risks and experiment without the threat of failing the course. I see this approach as the potential motivating and encouraging post-assessment practice. Therefore, I am trying to address and utilize Eyer’s recommendations at my classrooms [8-10].

Distinguishing Tests and Assessment

When the question “What is test?” is asked, the first definition that comes mind will be from dictionary. As a head-start, we would like to give a definition of a test from the Cambridge dictionary. The word test has three noun meanings in this dictionary. First meaning is that a test is a procedure intended to establish the quality, performance, or reliability of something, especially before it is taken into widespread use or a short written or spoken examination of a person's proficiency or knowledge, an event or situation that reveals the strength or quality of someone or something by putting them under strain. Second meaning: short for Test Match. Even though unrelated, the third meaning is connected with metallurgy: a movable hearth in a reverberating furnace, used for separating gold or silver from lead.

Assessment is an opinion or a judgment about somebody/something that has been thought about very carefully. In educational practice, assessment is an ongoing process that encompasses a wide range of methodological techniques. Whenever a student responds to a question, offers a comment, or tries out a new word or structure, the teacher subconsciously makes an appraisal of the student’s performance. A good teacher never ceases to assess students, whether those assessments are incidental or intended.

Tests, on the other hand, are a subset of assessment, a genre of assessment techniques. They are administrative procedures that occur identifiable times.

In scientific terms, a test is a method of measuring a person’s ability, knowledge, or performance in a given domain. I would like to make it more understandable. Firstly, a test is a method. It is an instrument – a set of techniques, procedures. The method must be explicit and structured in order to be a test. Second, test must measure. Some tests measure general ability, some focus on very specific objectives. Test measures an

individual's ability, knowledge or performance. Testers need to understand who the test takers are [11-13].

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